

Supplementary Figures 'Plasma protein profiles associated with anxiety and/or depressive symptoms in young IBD patients and the effect of cognitive behavioral therapy'

Supplementary Figure 1. Proteins associated to fecal calprotectin levels (unadjusted p value <0.05) Scatter plots of the association between fecal calprotectin and 7 proteins. P -values are not corrected for multiple testing.

Supplementary Figure 2. Proteins significantly associated to depressive symptoms in patients < 18 years

Scatter plots of the association between depressive symptoms in patients under the age of 18 with 10 different proteins. P-values are corrected for multiple testing.